

DETERMINATION OF INDICATIONS AND CONTRAINDICATIONS TO THE METHODS OF SURGICAL INTERVENTIONS IN CHRONIC CALCULOUS CHOLECYSTITIS AND CHOLEDOCHOLITHIASIS

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Relevance of the problem. Widespread development of minimally invasive technologies endoscopic, laparoscopic, minilaparotomy operations have become the methods of choice. However, there is still no single standard of treatment for this category of patients. The available methods of laparoscopic revision of the common bile duct are laborious and not always successful, and can lead to residual choledocholithiasis. In recent decades, LCE has been the "gold standard" in the surgical treatment of cholelithiasis. However, to this day, along with LCE, traditional methods of cholecystectomy (TCE) continue to be used, which is associated with the presence of absolute and relative contraindications.

The purpose of the work. Improving the results of the treatment of chronic calculous cholecystitis and its complications by optimizing the surgical tactics.

Materials and methods. This work is based on the analysis of the conducted examination and surgical treatment of 1929 patients with chronic calculous cholecystitis (CCC) and its complications. In accordance with the goals and objectives of the study, 1929 patients were conditionally divided into 2 groups. In the comparison group of 776 patients in 75 (9.6%) cases, cholecystectomy was performed through the traditional laparotomic approach (oblique incision in the right hypochondrium according to Fedorov - in 33 (4.2%), upper median laparotomy - in 42 (5.4%)), laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) - in 536 (69.1%) and mini-access cholecystectomy - in 165 (21.3%). In the main group of 1153 patients, in 76 (6.6%) cases, cholecystectomy was performed in the traditional way, LCE - in 715 (62.0%), from mini-approach - in 220 (19.1%) and from mini-approach with using instruments of original design - in 142 (12.3%).

Results and discussion. As the experience of surgical treatment in chronic CC and choledocholithiasis was accumulated and their analysis led us to determine the indications and contraindications for the choice of the operation method, which contributed to the optimization of surgical tactics.

Advantages of traditional cholecystectomy: Traditional cholecystectomy (CE) is performed from upper median or oblique subcostal incisions according to

Kocher and Fedorov, which provide wide access to the gallbladder, extrahepatic bile ducts, liver, pancreas and duodenum. The disadvantages are: significant trauma to the structures of the anterior abdominal wall, a significant number of early and late wound complications; an increased risk of thromboembolic complications and adhesive process; significant cosmetic defect.

Advantages of laparoscopic operations: instead of a wide incision of the abdominal wall (from 7 to 30 cm in length), three to five trocar punctures of 0.5-1 cm are performed. As a result:

- 1) there are no severe pains in the postoperative period;
- 2) cosmetic effect;
- 3) the duration of stay in the hospital after the operation is up to 3-4 days;
- 4) 14-15 days after the operation, you can start normal work and household activities;
- 5) purulent-septic complications, as well as postoperative hernias are extremely rare;
- 6) the ability to diagnose and operate a combined surgical pathology on different floors of the abdominal cavity.

Contraindications:

- the risk of anesthesia of 3 and 4 degrees with an unstable course of concomitant diseases;
- previously transferred open large operations on the organs of the upper floor of the abdominal cavity;
- uncorrected blood clotting disorders;
- the level of intra-abdominal pressure is more than 15 mm Hg. Art.;
- III trimester of pregnancy;
- under conditions of sufficiently intense pneumoperitoneum (injection of gas into the abdominal cavity), which raises the diaphragm and impairs its mobility, which has a negative effect on cardiac and respiratory functions.

Modified mini-approach cholecystectomy may be performed in patients with high anesthetic risk and comorbidities for which laparoscopy is contraindicated. Advantages: the possibility of CE with any body type of the patient; reduction of trauma - minimal damage to the anterior abdominal wall; the postoperative course is not much different from LCE; reducing the risk of postoperative complications; the ability to operate on patients who have previously undergone operations on the anterior abdominal wall; reduction of the length of stay in the hospital up to 3-4 days; there is no need to use narcotic analgesics; the

technique can be applied in the second and third trimesters of pregnancy; the possibility of applying cosmetic skin sutures.

Comparative evaluation of the results of surgical treatment of patients with CCC showed that, following the indications and contraindications for the choice of surgical tactics in chronic calculous cholecystitis and choledocholithiasis, the frequency of iatrogenic injuries decreased from 1.5% to 3.3%, postoperative complications associated with surgery - from 6, 3 to 0.6%, mortality from 1.2% to 0.2%, and the need for repeated traditional interventions decreased from 1.1% to 0%, conversions after mini-access and LCE from 7.5% to 0.5% ($p=0.005$).

Conclusion. Thus, by specifying the role and place of each of the CE methods, with the definition of indications, advantages and disadvantages of each of the methods, it is possible to optimize the surgical tactics and improve the results of treatment in the surgical treatment of cholecystocholedocholithiasis.

